

Studies on physico-chemical properties of cyproheptadine in water and water-methanol mixtures

G. Bandyopadhyay^a and S. C. Lahiri^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kalyani Govt. Engineering College, Kalyani-741 235, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, India

E-mail : sujitclahiri@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 5 March 2003, accepted 30 September 2003

Solubility of cyproheptadine and cyproheptadine hydrochloride in water and partition coefficients of cyproheptadine between *n*-octanol and water at different pHs were determined at 298 K. Ionisation constants of cyproheptadine in water-methanol mixtures were determined pH-metrically and extrapolated to zero methanol concentration to have the p*K* value of cyproheptadine in water. The result was confirmed spectrophotometrically utilising phosphate buffers. The p*K* value suggests molecular cyproheptadine to be more effective physiologically.

Physico-chemical properties of drugs are of great interest to understand 'drug action' at the molecular level. The observations of Elrich¹ and Langley² "whatever effects a drug produces in a biologic system must be regarded as ultimate consequences of physico-chemical interactions between that drug and functionally important molecules in the living organism (known as receptors)³", mark the beginning of the theory of drug-receptor interactions and correlation of physico-chemical and physiological properties of drugs. The first step is the association of the drug (D) with the receptor (R) molecule to form complex DR which triggers biologic action, ($D + R \rightleftharpoons DR$). The complex DR is usually stabilised by ionic, covalent and coordinate covalent bonding. In most cases a multiplicity of physical and chemical interactions like van der Waals interactions, charge transfer, hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions etc. are involved in the stabilisation of the complexes⁴⁻⁷. Most of the drugs are usually weak acids or bases (almost insoluble in water) but they are administered as salts. The reasons are (i) modification of physico-chemical properties such as solubility, stability, photosensitivity and organoleptic characteristics, (ii) improvement of bio-availability and (iii) reduction in toxicity. It has been observed that ionisation

plays an important part in drug activities. A positive correlation between ionisation and biological action was first made by Albert *et al.*⁹.

It has been observed that aminoacridines are antibacterial in the cationic forms whereas phenols are active in the molecular forms^{9,10}. Similarly, correlation of biologic activities of drugs and their partition coefficients between *n*-octanol and water introduced by Hansch^{10,11}, forms the basis of structure-activity relationship. It has widely been accepted and used^{4,10-12}. These considerations prompted us to determine (i) solubility of cyproheptadine and cyproheptadine hydrochloride in water, (ii) partition coefficient of cyproheptadine between *n*-octanol and water and (iii) ionisation constant of cyproheptadine in methanol-water mixtures and in water. The results are described in this communication.

Results

Solubilities of cyproheptadine hydrochloride and cyproheptadine are given in Table 1.

The thermodynamic ionization constant for the dissociation of cyproheptadine cation, can be represented as

Table 1. Spectrophotometric determination of solubilities and partition coefficient of cyproheptadine.HCl (CypHCl) and cyproheptadine (Cyp)

Drug	Solubility (mol L ⁻¹)	Partition coefficient $P_{\text{octanol/water}}$	log <i>P</i>
CypHCl	1.075×10^{-2} (water)	$2.81 (\pm 0.02) \times 10^4$ (pH = 5.62)	4.46
Cyp	6.10×10^{-5} (water)	$1.63 (\pm 0.03) \times 10^3$ (pH = 7.45)	3.21
Cyp	1.385×10^{-2} (<i>n</i> -octanol)	$2.21 (\pm 0.02) \times 10^2$ (pH = 8.92)	2.36

Isosbestic wavelengths for CypHCl and Cyp are 250 nm and 265 nm.

$$K = \frac{[\text{L}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{LH}^+] \cdot \gamma_{\text{L}} \cdot \gamma_{\text{H}^+} / \gamma_{\text{LH}^+}} \approx \frac{[\text{L}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{LH}^+]} \quad (2)$$

By convention $\gamma_{\text{L}} \approx 1$ and for 1 : 1 electrolytes at low ionic strengths, $\gamma_{\text{H}^+} = \gamma_{\text{LH}^+}$

$$\text{p}K = -\log [\text{H}^+] - \log \frac{[\text{L}]}{[\text{LH}^+]} \quad (3)$$

where, $-\log [\text{H}^+] = B + \log U_{\text{H}}$ (4)

B is the 'meter reading' of the solution in mixed solvents and $\log U_{\text{H}}$ is the appropriate correction term which vary from solvent to solvent¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Meter readings after correction gives H^+ ion concentrations and the difference in the $[\text{H}^+]$ ion concentrations between the experimental solution and the blank solution give $[\text{H}^+]^{15-19}$. Thus from the relations (5) and (6) and using eq. (3) the $\text{p}K$ values were obtained.

$$[\text{LH}^+] \rightleftharpoons [\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}} - [\text{H}^+] \quad (5)$$

$$[\text{L}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{L}] + [\text{LH}^+] \quad (6)$$

where $[\text{L}]_{\text{T}}$, represents 'total' concentration of cyproheptadine.

However, for spectrophotometric determination of the dissociation constant of cyproheptadine in water, H^+ ion activities of the solutions were measured.

The equation used for $\text{p}K$ determination is

$$\text{p}K = \text{pH} - \log \frac{(d_i - d)}{(d - d_m)} - \log \gamma_{\pm} \quad (7)$$

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = 0.509 \sqrt{\mu} (1 + aB \sqrt{\mu}) \quad (8)$$

a has been taken to be 6.7 \AA (calculated). d_i , d_m and d represent the optical densities of the ionic, molecular forms

Table 2. Spectrophotometric determination of $\text{p}K$ of cyproheptadine in water

pH	d	$\log \frac{d_i - d}{d - d_m}$	$\text{p}K$	Thermodynamic $\text{p}K$
7.9	0.638	-0.798	8.69	
8.15	0.620	-0.557	8.71	
8.45	0.588	-0.253	8.70	
8.70	0.556	0.0	8.70	8.65 ± 0.01
9.15	0.501	0.462	8.69	
9.27	0.490	0.581	8.69	
9.50	0.474	0.798	8.70	

Analytical wavelength for Cyp = 238 nm, ionic strength = 0.0125 and $-\log \gamma_{\pm} = 0.05$ ($\gamma_{\pm} \rightarrow$ mean ionic activity coefficient).

d_m (optical density of the molecular form) = 0.443 and d_i (optical density of the ionic form) = 0.669.

and the equilibrium mixtures of ionic and molecular forms

in buffer solutions. The $\text{p}K$ -values are given in Table 2.

Partition coefficients of the cyproheptadine between n -octanol and water is given by

$$P = C_{\text{cyp}}(\text{octanol}) / C_{\text{cyp}}(\text{water}) \quad (9)$$

The relation is valid only if there is no association or dissociation of the ligand in any of the phases. However, the $\text{p}K$ -value of cyproheptadine cation has been found to be 8.65 which means that cyproheptadine can be present as cyproheptadine only above $\text{pH} = 10$. Thus at any pH

$$(\text{Cyp})_{\text{total}}(\text{water}) = (\text{Cyp})_{\text{water}} + (\text{CypH}^+)_{\text{water}} \quad (10)$$

From the total concentration of $(\text{Cyp})_{\text{T}}$ and $\text{p}K$ -value, $(\text{Cyp})_{\text{eq}}$ at any pH in water were calculated from which P (partition coefficient) were determined. The partition coefficients calculated are given in Table 3.

Discussion

The solubility of cyproheptadine hydrochloride and cyproheptadine in water at 298 K are $1.075 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/L}^{-1}$ and $6.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/L}^{-1}$. The solubility of cyproheptadine in n -octanol can be roughly taken to be $1.385 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/L}^{-1}$ at 298 K taking partition coefficient P to be equal to 2.27×10^2 at $\text{pH} = 8.92$. The partition coefficient value of cyproheptadine between n -octanol and water at $\text{pH} = 7.45$ is $P = 1.63 \times 10^3$ i.e. it has been found that P value changes with pH of the aqueous solution. $\text{p}K$ value of cyproheptadine is 8.65 at 298 K i.e. cyproheptadine will be present predominantly as cation (CypH^+) at low pH s. The variation of P with pH is known²² and in this case it may be due to slight solubility of CypH^+ in n -octanol and slight solubility of water in n -octanol²². P values can be obtained at higher pH (above 11) but the formation of base may be a possibility. $\text{p}K$ values of cyproheptadine at 298 K have been observed to decrease monotonically with increasing methanol concentration similar to those observed in case of isoelectric reactions, $\text{LH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{L} + \text{H}^+$ (where $\text{L} = 2,2'$ -bipyridine or 1,10-phenanthroline^{17-19,23,24}). The $\text{p}K$ values of cyproheptadine in water and methanol at 298 K by extrapolation come out to be 8.70 and 7.00 respectively. The $\text{p}K$ value in water at 298 K obtained spectrophotometrically is 8.65 in agreement with the value obtained by extrapolation.

The decrease in $\text{p}K$ values in methanol-water mixtures cannot be ascribed solely due to the decrease in dielectric constant but solute-solvent interactions are also important. The solvent effect on the dissociation of CypH^+ may not be of great bearing on the biological activities but it is important from physico-chemical point of view. The Gibbs energy

Table 3. Dissociation constants of cyproheptadine in methanol-water mixtures and free energy of transfer of hydrogen ion from water to methanol-water mixtures

Wt% of MeOH	pK	ΔG^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G_{(1)}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G_1^0(\text{H}^+)$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G_{(1)}^0 - \Delta G_1^0(\text{H}^+)$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
0	8.65 (±0.01)* (8.70)	49.33	-	-	-
25.5	8.30	47.34	-1.99	-1.8	-0.2
34.73	8.10	46.20	-3.13	-2.1	-1.0
44.38	7.90	45.05	-4.28	-3.2	-1.1
54.48	7.65	43.63	-5.70	-4.0	-1.7
65.06	7.50	42.77	-6.56	-5.0	-1.6
76.15	7.40	42.20	-7.13	-5.5	-1.6
87.18	7.20	41.40	-7.93	-5.1	-2.8

* Spectrophotometric value. Value in the bracket is from extrapolation.

change for the reaction (1) is,

$$\Delta G^0 = 2.303 RT \text{ pK} \quad (11)$$

The Gibbs energy of transfer ΔG_1^0 for the reaction (1) in going from water to methanol-water mixtures can be written as,

$$\Delta G_1^0(1) = \Delta G_1^0(\text{Cyp}) + \Delta G_1^0(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_1^0(\text{CypH}^+) \quad (12)$$

$$\text{or, } \Delta G_1^0(\text{Cyp}) - \Delta G_1^0(\text{CypH}^+) = \Delta G_1^0(1) - \Delta G_1^0(\text{H}^+) \quad (13)$$

(Cyp → Cyproheptadine and CypH⁺ → Cyproheptadine cation)

*JICS-3*The values are given in Table 3. $\Delta G_1^0(\text{H}^+)$ values in methanol-water mixtures were taken from the literature^{15,16}. The results indicate that [$\Delta G_1^0(\text{Cyp}) - \Delta G_1^0(\text{CypH}^+)$] is increasingly negative though the values are small. Solubility of Cyp in methanol-water mixture should increase with increase in methanol, i.e. $\Delta G_1^0(\text{Cyp})$ should be negative. However, CypHCl is known to be fairly soluble in methanol, i.e. $\Delta G_1^0(\text{CypH}^+)$ is also negative. The physiological activity of cyproheptadine can be either due to its cationic form CypH⁺ which is predominant in the physiological pH range or due to neutral Cyp.

Since the pK-value of CypH⁺ is 8.65, a small change in pH value may have wide effect on its biological activities. The biological activities of barbiturates and antihistamines are very much dependent on pH and pK⁹. It may be argued that like acridine which has strong antibacterial activities as cation, the physiological activities of Cyp may be due to its cationic form. Many of the antihistaminic drugs have pK-values between (9.0–9.7)²⁵ so that the drugs at the physiological pH (7.4–7.8) are predominantly cationic in nature. The possibility of formation of ion pair by combi-

nation of the drugs as CypH⁺ with anionic group of the receptor (or bacterium) is a distinct probability.

The complexes are usually stabilized by ionic bonds supplemented by multiple H-bonds, CT bond or van der Waals bond. However, cyproheptadine is an effective H₁-blocker and possesses mild central nervous depressing activities. It is a specific blocker of 5-HT receptors i.e. it has antiserotonin function²⁶. Cyproheptadine has been found to form charge transfer and hydrogen bond complexes with different acceptors and hydrogen bonding is usually associated with drug-receptor interactions⁵. These facts indicate that cyproheptadine is likely to be active as neutral molecule which makes drug penetration into the membrane and absorption in lipid quite easy. From the pK and P values, it can be assumed that drug acts preferably in the alkali region (pH = 8–9), i.e. as neutral cyproheptadine molecule. Naturally the drug may not be very effective to persons suffering from hyperacidity.

Experimental

Cyproheptadine hydrochloride (Central Drug Laboratory, Kolkata) was dissolved in water and ammonium hydroxide was added dropwisely to the solution till the precipitation of the molecular form is complete. The filtered precipitate was repeatedly washed to remove excess ammonia, dried and recrystallised from alcohol.

Determination of solubility of cyproheptadine hydrochloride and cyproheptadine :

Cyproheptadine hydrochloride (I) is fairly soluble in water but cyproheptadine (II) is almost insoluble in water but both are soluble in methanol and methanol-water mixtures. Therefore, spectra of I and II were measured in methanol-water (50% v/v) mixtures and isobestic points (265 and 260 nm having almost the same absorptivity values) were utilized for the determination of solubility values. The linear calibration curves obtained from the plot of absorptivities against concentrations in water indicate that both I and II obey Lambert-Beer's law at low concentrations ($1 \times 10^{-5} - 4 \times 10^{-5} M$ for I and $0.6 \times 10^{-5} - 4 \times 10^{-5} M$ for II). For the determination of solubility of the compounds in water, saturated solutions of the compounds were prepared in Campbell solubility apparatus¹³ immersed and stirred in a thermostat maintained at $298 \pm 0.02 K$ for 16 h so as to attain equilibrium. The solubilities of I and II were determined by comparing the absorptivity values of the appropriately diluted (10^3 times for I and 2 times for II) saturated solutions with those of the standard calibration curves at the desired wavelengths.

Partition coefficient of cyproheptadine between *n*-octanol and water :

For the determination of partition coefficient, definite amounts of cyproheptadine taken in *n*-octanol were mixed with 100 ml water at three different pHs (5.62, 7.45 and 8.92) and shaken for three hours. The solutions were allowed to equilibrate in the thermostat maintained at $298 \pm 0.02 K$.

The concentrations of cyproheptadine in two layers (water and *n*-octanol) were determined from optical density measurements at 286 nm from which partition coefficients were determined. At higher pHs (above pH = 9), turbidity appears in aqueous phase probably due to the formation of the cyproheptadine hydroxide.

Dissociation constant of cyproheptadine cation :

In view of limitations (low solubility of cyproheptadine in water and choice of buffers is not possible without the knowledge of approximate p*K*-values) of determining p*K*-values in water spectrophotometrically, p*K*-values of cyproheptadine cation in methanol + water mixtures were determined pH-metrically. Definite amount of cyproheptadine ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) was acidified to different extents by HClO₄ and H⁺ concentrations of the equilibrium mixtures were measured pH-metrically. The H⁺ concentrations of the blank solutions (without cyproheptadine) were also measured. The data were utilized to calculate p*K*-values. The experiment was repeated in different percentages of the mixed solvents. However, due to solu-

bility limitation the experiment could not be performed in water and even below 30% v/v of methanol.

The pH-meter readings in mixed solvents do not give H⁺ ion activities or concentrations as the glass electrode cannot be standardized with suitable buffer of known H⁺ ion activities. The H⁺ ion concentrations can be obtained using a glass-calomel electrode combination after suitable calibration to obtain 'correction terms' to convert the meter readings in mixed solvents into H⁺ ion concentrations in the way described in earlier communications¹³⁻¹⁷.

The p*K*-values in mixed solvents thus determined are given in Table I and the p*K*-value in water was obtained from suitable extrapolation. The result was confirmed spectrophotometrically. For the spectrophotometric determination the spectra of cyproheptadine ($10^{-5} M$) in 0.1 *N* HCl ($\lambda_{max} = 286 nm$) and 0.1 *N* NaOH ($\lambda_{max} = 284 nm$) were obtained from which the isobestic point and the

Fig. 1. The spectra of cyproheptadine in 0.1 *N* HCl (A) and in 0.1 *N* NaOH (B).

analytical wavelength (238 nm) were determined (Fig. 1). From the absorptivity readings of definite concentrations ($\sim 2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$) in 0.1 *N* HClO₄, 0.1 *N* NaOH and in a number of buffer solutions (Na₂HPO₄ and NaH₂PO₄) of pH range 7.9–9.50 (measured pH-metrically) at the analytical wavelength, the dissociation constant p*K* of cyproheptadine was calculated. The pH and spectro-photometric measurements were made using an Orion pH-meter model 720A

and Jasco model 7850 UV/Vis spectrophotometer.

References

1. P. Elrich, *Lancet.*, 1913, **2**, 445.
2. J. N. Langley, *J. Physiol. (London)*, 1978, **1**, 339.
3. A. Goldstein, L. Aronow and S. M. Kalman, "In Principles of Drug Action", 2nd. ed., Wiley and Sons, New York, 1974, pp. 1-127.
4. A. Korolkovas, "In Essentials of Medicinal Chemistry", 2nd. ed., Wiley and Sons, New York, 1988, pp. 140-172.
5. J. Gangopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2000, **214**, 169.
6. J. Gangopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2001, **215**, 837.
7. J. Gangopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2001, **215**, 883.
8. A. Albert, S. Rubbo and R. Goldacre, *Nature (London)*, 1941, **147**, 332.
9. A. Albert, "Selective Toxicity", 6th. ed., Chapman and Hall, New York, 1979, pp. 330-384.
10. C. Hansch and T. Fujita, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1610.
11. C. Hansch, "In Drug Design", ed. E. Ariens, 1971, **1**, 271.
12. S. P. Gupta, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1109.
13. A. N. Campbell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 179.
14. U. C. Bhattacharyya and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1966, **50**, 131.
15. S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 319.
16. D. Sengupta, A. Pal and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 2685.
17. R. Mondal and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1999, **210**, 157.
18. R. Mondal and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2000, **214**, 1.
19. G. Bandyopadhyay and S. C. Lahiri, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 2001, **215**, 37.
20. S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *Z. Physik. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1964, **41**, 173.
21. "Clarke's Isolation and Identification of Drugs", 2nd. ed., Senior Consulting Editor, Moffat A. C. London, The Pharmaceutical Press, 1986 pp. 505-506.
22. A. T. Florence and D. Allwood, "Physico-chemical Principles of Pharmacy", 2nd. ed., Macmillan Press, London, 1985, pp. 161-170.
23. D. K. Hazra and S. C. Lahiri, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **79**, 385.
24. D. K. Hazra and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 567.
25. A. T. Florence and D. Attwood, "Physico-chemical Principles of Pharmacy", 2nd. ed., Macmillan Press, London, 1985, pp. 64-67.
26. Martindale, "The Extra Pharmacopia", ed. Reynolds E. F. James, The Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1993, p. 935.